

Hybrid rice

Evaluation of hybrid rices for ratooning ability

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Hybrid rice was developed in China. About 6 million ha of irrigated land are planted to F₁ hybrids that yield 20-30% more than the best semidwarf, nonhybrid varieties. Hybrid rice also should yield well in some rainfed lowland conditions on account of their early seedling and vegetative vigor and strong, deep, root system. A successful ratoon from the hybrid rice crop under rainfed lowland conditions might help compensate for the extra cost of hybrid seed, which is estimated to be three to four times more than that of nonhybrid varieties.

We evaluated 57 rice hybrids and 5 check varieties for ratooning ability at the IRRI farm in the 1983 dry season.

Hybrids and checks were ratooned by cutting the stalks 15 cm above the ground at maturity. Immediately after cutting 40 kg N/ha was topdressed. Ratooning ability was rated 3 weeks later.

Ratooning ability varied widely. IR56 and 14 hybrids performed consistently well in 2 or more replications. Mean regeneration for hybrids varied from 62 to 97% (see table). However, all had 70% or higher regeneration in at least 2 replications. IR56 had 90 to 100% regenerations, except in 1 of 9 plots where it had only 40 to 50%. However, it had only 10-11 tillers/hill and 8-9 panicles/hill. In some hybrids with relatively poor regeneration, missing hills were compensated for by the many tillers and panicles per successful hill. Hybrid ratoons were more vigorous than those of IR56.

Ratoon height Varied from 51 cm to 70 cm. Hybrid IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR36 had the most tillers and panicles/m². Because the experiment ended before maturity, number of tillers and panicles/m² may not truly reflect yield potential.

Hybrids with IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A in their parentage had high regeneration and vigorous ratoons. Because the parents of

Plant characters of rice hybrids screened for ratooning ability. IRRI, 1983 dry season (av of 3 replications).

Hybrid, variety	Regeneration (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Total tillers (no./m ²)	Tillers (no./hill)	Total panicles (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./hill)	Viral disease rating
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR56 ^a	70	65	279	11	189	8	1
IR10154-23-3-3A/IR15795-232-3-3-2 ^b	69	51	323	13	149	6	1
IR56 (check)	81	62	284	10	179	6	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR36 ^a	97	65	515	15	423	12	1
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR48 ^c	81	60	389	14	145	6	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR19661-364-1-2-3 ^b	68	61	329	14	171	8	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR19735-5-2-3-2-1 ^a	93	64	485	15	420	13	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR19729-67-3	83	68	301	10	246	8	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR13146-45-2-3 ^d	62	58	325	15	401 ^d	18	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR10781-143-2-3 ^e	68	—	346	15	—	—	0
IR19799-17-3-1-1A/IR13420-6-3-3-1	83	55	349	12	231	8	0
IR19799-17-3-1-1A/IR2797-125-3-2-2	81	70	353	12	274	10	1
IR56 (check)	93	60	348	11	294	9	0
MR365A/IR19661-364-1-2-3 ^a	68	69	327	14	218	9	0
MR365A/IR19661-131-1-2 ^b	64	67	337	15	213	10	0
MR365A/IR48	80	65	378	14	307	9	1
IR56 (check)	93	56	348	11	307	9	0

^a In one replication, plants were mostly vegetative, flowering started. ^b In more than one replication, plants were mostly vegetative, flowering started. ^c Based on two replications; in third replication, plants were in Vegetative phase. ^d Based on one replication; in two other replications, flowering did not occur. ^e Vegetative plants only in all three replications.

the hybrids were not evaluated, it is difficult to predict the bases of good ratooning ability. Whether this parent line has dominant genes for ratooning ability or whether ratooning resulted from heterosis needs further investigation. In one of the crosses (IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR36), however, good ratooning ability seems to be due to dominant gene(s) in the parent line because IR36 showed consistently poor ratooning.

Different responses of some hybrids and IR56 in different replications suggested that besides genetic factors, cultural management factors may influence ratooning ability. F₂ populations of the hybrids and their parents should be evaluated for ratooning in subsequent studies. □

New maintainers and restorers for Chinese cytoplasmic-genetic male-sterile lines

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We sought to identify new maintainers and restorers for the Chinese male-sterile lines: Zhen Shan 97A, Er-Jiu- Nan 1A, and V20A.

Bhavani, BPI 76-1/CO 42, Basmati mutant, and Pusa 169-33-1-1 are good maintainers. CRM 13-32-1 11 and ADT33 are partial maintainers which have not been reported until now (Table 1). We also identified three new restorers: IR30, Pusa 150-21-1-1, and Pusa 167- 120-3-2 (Table 2). Although they are good

Table 1. Maintainers to Chinese cytoplasmic-genetic male-sterile lines, New Delhi.

Test cross	Pollen sterility (%)
Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/ CRM13-32-111	83.3
Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/ Pusa 169-33-1-1	98.3
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/Bhavani	100.0
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/BPI 76-1	100.0
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/CO 42	100.0
V20A/Basmati mutant	100.0
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/ADT33	83.3

restorers, they have not been evaluated for agronomic value in terms of exploitable hybrid vigor. They are, however,

promising because they have stable yield performance, good maturity, and good cooking quality. □

Table 2. Restorer lines for Chinese cytoplasmic-genetic male-sterile lines, New Delhi.

Test cross	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet fertility (%)
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/IR30	4.8	93
Zhen Shan 97A/Pusa 167-120-3-2	8.5	92
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/Pusa 150-21-1-1	5.0	93.5

Evaluation of some cytoplasmic male sterile (cms), maintainer, and restorer lines in Bangladesh

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Thirty-two rice varieties or lines including a set of 5 cms and 5 maintainer lines, and a set of 9 maintainer and 13 restorer lines

supplied by IRRI were evaluated for stability, adaptability, and agronomic suitability under Bangladesh agroclimatic conditions. The tests were held at the BRRI-Joydebpur station in 1982 aman (Jul-Dec).

Each entry was transplanted in a 2.5-m single row at 25- × 25-cm spacing with one 30-day-old seedling per hill in a randomized complete block design with 2 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 60-25-15 kg NPK/ha. Agronomic and flowering traits were recorded and reaction to

bacterial leaf blight and sheath rot was noted.

Only one cms line, Pankhari 203A, and its maintainer Pankhari 203B performed better under local conditions. However, pollen sterility in the cms lines was incomplete. Two other maintainers — IR19657-87-3-3 and IET3257 — and six restorer lines also showed good adaptability (see table). Performance of cms lines V20A, Wu 10A, and Ms 577A was poor although they had good stability (95-100% pollen sterility). □

Cms, maintainer, and restorer lines that performed well in Bangladesh.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 1st flowering	Days to complete flowering	Panicles (no./plant)	Flag leaf length (cm)	Disease		Phenotypic acceptability		Pollen fertility (%)
						BLB	ShR	Vegetative stage	Maturity	
Pankhari 203A	115	17	88	21	27.3	5	5	3	5	15-25
Pankhari 203B	128	83	91	14	29.4	5	5	3	5	80-90
IR19657-87-3-3	97	93	111	13	31.5	1	2	4	4	85-95
IET3257	92	94	106	9	28.1	1	2	4	6	80-90
IR26	84	102	119	24	31.4	1	1	5	5	85-90
IR42	90	101	118	15	27.9	2	1	4	5	80-85
IR46	106	94	111	17	26.4	1	1	4	2	75-80
IR52	96	86	104	16	32.6	1	1	5	5	80-90
IR54	98	93	107	17	28.4	1	1	4	3	80-90
IR2307-247-2-2-3	83	88	107	17	31.3	1	1	5	5	80-85

Extent of natural outcrossing of V20A, a cytoplasmic male-sterile (cms) line, in Bangladesh

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BRRI initiated collaborative research on hybrid rice with IRRI in 1982. Successful hybrid rice production depends on

large amounts of outcrossing of cms lines. We studied field production of hybrid seed using cms line V20A and its maintainer, V20B (pollen source).

Twenty-five 25-day-old V20B seedlings were transplanted 1 seedling/hill in 5 rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing in an isolated plot. At the same time 30-day-old V20A seedlings were planted around V20B seedlings at various distances — 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 cm — to maintain the same spacing and seedlings/hill as in

V20B. Only one panicle of each V20A plant was bagged before anthesis. The

Percent seed set on V20A at various distances from the pollen source V20B, BRRI, 1982.

Distance (cm) from V20B	Seed set (%) on V20A
20	2.51
40	1.45
60	0.93
80	0.79
100	0.59